

IMPACT OF STRESS ON THE STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A CASE STUDY OF KHAIRPUR MIR'S

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Abstract

Purpose-The main purpose of this study is to study the impact of stress on the students' performance in Higher Educational Institutions: A case study of Khairpur Mirs'

Design/Methodology/Approach- The study advocates the quantitative nature. The targeted population for this study is the students of Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur and Benazir Bhutto Shaheed University of Technical and Skills Development Khairpur Mirs'. Hypotheses were generated on the basis of literature suggested. A survey questionnaire (five point Likert scale) is used to collect the data and analyzed through Smart PLS software.

Findings- The major findings of study poses that the stress is significantly associated with the students' performance it may cause a positive or a negative change on students' performance.

Research Limitations/Implications-This study has practical implications in the students' life. Stress can shine their academic life or may damage their personal life as well due to academic stress.

Originality/Value- This study is first to be conducted in Higher Educational Institutes of Khairpur Mirs'.

INTRODUCTION

Past research shows that some undergraduate students significantly experience stress (Bennett, 2003). First-year university students were found to be particularly prone to stress (Yaffe, 2000) and experience high levels of stress (Wintre & Yaffe, 2000) due to the college life transition many of them face culture shock as university life is different from school life. Failing to cope with the stressors during

the transition may cause deterioration of academic performance and increase of psychological distress (Wang, 2005). The increase in stress during the first year predicted the decrease of overall adjustment and lower grade point average (GPA) (Wintre & Yaffe, 2000). Students tend to lose self-confidence having to establish new social relations and at the same time trying to cope with the increasing academic demands

(Bellerose, 2000). A list of ten sources of stress was identified among the first year students and the stressors include tests and examinations, the big range of content to be learnt, lack of time to do revision, poor marks, having self-expectation, insufficient skill in practice, fail to follow the reading schedule, heavy workload, having difficulty in understanding the content and fail to provide answers to teachers' questions (Yusoff et al., 2010).

Academic performance is the educational aim that is achieved by a student, teacher or institution achieves over a specific time. The academic performance of students heavily depends upon the parental involvement in their academic activities to attain the higher level of quality in academic success. The students are quite emotional especially females. They are take stress in everything at school level. A lot of factor that influence in their study like present pressure, teacher's attitude towards their study, home strictness, future and job tensions (Hussain et al, 2012).

Stress is one of basic psychological aspects of human behavior. Stress is mental condition of an individual under strain. Being unable to cope and deal with the situation is called stress. Stress can be defined as a mental pressure caused by any event or situation in someone's life. Several studies have been conducted to measure the different aspects and factors of stress and its effects and impacts on various folds of life.

Stress can be very destructive and subtle. In fact, for an ordinary person it is hard to understand all dimensions of stress and its effect on human health. Specially, mental health. Stress can cause severe mental issues and disorders, if not recognized and prevented at right time. In addition to that, definition of stress can vary from person to person, because of the dissimilar mental, personal, professional and academic conditions of individuals. In this modern era of competition, hustling and hectic routines, every person has to cope with stress at some extent. Regardless of his age, career, gender, surrounding or educational background. Lower stress levels can be managed and ignored to some level, but coping with higher stress levels on regular basic can cause serious health issues.

Body's physiological and psychological response in order to be adjusted in new circumstances can also be called stress (Franken, 1994). Strain or exceedance of

a person's capacity to contend with an event can be called stress (Lahey, 2004). An nonprofessional person may explain stress in terms of anxiety, depression, undesirable surrounding powers, sentimental reaction and tension (Ogden J. , 2004). Physical stress can occur due to many different things, which may include fear of something life-threatening, or it can be attached with feelings like, care for family, or concern about career or poor results in academics. Response to things in one's surrounding can become source of stress (Manuel et. al, 2003).

Stress is one of widely studied topic in professional and academic fields around the globe. Although many studies have been conducted to measure and recognize the impacts and effect of stress in academic world. Yet, very little have been done to measure the impacts of stress on the performance of students of higher education institutions of Sindh and no study of this kind have been conducted in higher education institutions of Khairpur Mirs.

As every other aspect of life, stress is a common phenomenon among the students. From very start of academic life to the higher levels of education existence of stress cannot be denied. Level of stress can vary at different stages or phases of academic journey, but the presence of stress is constant throughout the odyssey and as well as throughout the life. Stress can also be defined as any psychological event which challenges or endanger our well-being.

Feelings linked with unease, fear, worry and anxiety and nervousness produce stress. Which lead towards the emptiness, hopelessness, helplessness, depression, worthlessness, irritation and restlessness? These are the alarming sign for the health of an individual and should be prevented on time. Stress can be controlled and people try to find the way through which they can reduce the stress, sometimes stress becomes intolerable. It is critical to understand and realize when the stress is uncontrollable.

1.1 Academic Stress

In academic, different demands, responsibilities, contending with different academic projects and meeting the requirements of academic standards causes stress. Confronting personal, family, emotional and social issues causes stress and impacts the mental capacity of learning and academic performance

(Chewgrahan Rogers & Yassin, 2003; Fish & Nies, 1996).

Higher educational institutions not only provide students with advance degrees in their selective subjects but also evaluate their psychological standing. Higher educational institutions or universities not only allow their students to pursue their academic degrees, but also provide platforms to their students to socialize with other students, teachers, and visitors, participate in different activities and experience psychological growth. Many studies have discovered that pursuing a degree in a university can induce stress or mental strain (Gall et. al, 2000). This is because students of universities have to confront with a tough academic system, way of living and social surroundings. Students of higher educational institutions have to attain certain levels of educational accomplishments to successfully complete a degree. The academic accomplishment is determined by the academic performance of a student based on various academic aspect including, semesters, classroom presentations, assignments, participation in speech sessions etc (Ong, 2009).

Stress can strain the students of higher educational institutions from concentrating and enjoying learning by behaving in a harmonious way, and to evolve their unparalleled endowment. Accumulation of stress can cause worry, academic depression, misery, nervousness and can conduce to hyperactivity disorder or attention deficit, asocial attitude and even vehement acts. Stress and academic stress is one of the widely discussed topics of modern times.

Different studies conducted earlier indicate that students of higher education institutes go through different levels of stress (Brown, 1999). Students of higher education institutions face significant levels of stress during their first years (Towbes, 1996). Students face difficulty in transaction from college to university life. Failing to cope with such transaction can cause devaluation of academic performance and rise in psychological suffering (Dwyer, 2001). Increased stress levels during the initial academic year at university anticipate the decline in overall performance and lower grades (Wintre, 2000). Students may lose their self-confidence in coping with new environment, interacting with new people and attempt to deal with their extensive academic requirements (Tao, 2000). Many students have

expressed dissatisfaction of feeling stressed with regard to their studies, when facing the competition in exams or grade as well enormous amounts of information and inadequate time to cope with such amount of knowledge to master the exams (Carveth, 1996).

Regardless of the source stress, it can also be an important factor in life of a student. Stress can also serve as a positive factor in academic life. Stress is not always negative there is a positive side of stress. It can contribute as much to positive side as much as it can to positive side. A student who have prepared for exams due to the stress is called positive stress and stress which caused due to no adequate preparation for exam is negative stress.

Stress should be balanced adequately, this adequate balancing can make stress a positive element of our lives. Furthermore, stress in certain aspects, right circumstances and at adequate level can increase productivity and performance of a students to a certain level. After that certain level stress can be really destructive and can quickly deteriorate things stated by Paul J. Rosch, M.D. (2007), and President of American Institute of Stress. Constructive use of stress is depend upon the emphasis of the stress as a performance increaser and as stress as a constrain.

Therefore, it is essential for students of higher education institutions to understand the boundaries which are drawn by stress, and try to exceed and excel those boundaries in a way which can encourage them to use this negative factor in a positive and constructive manner, to help improve and enhance their academic performance and overall capabilities and skills.

1.2 Personal factors

Many elements affect the student's academic performance. Personal factors are one of them and can be broadly categorized or classified into-academic and non-academic factors. Factors like family background, pre-schooling background, college environment, learning habits, sleeping habits and personal characteristics. M. H. Muhdin (2016) stated in his study that family's financial conditions, sleeping routine and duration, study method and habit are the important personal factors which affect the academic performance of a student.

According to the study of S. P. Singh et al., (2016) learning facilities, proper counselling from parents and communication skills have a positive significant effect on the performance of a student. Zekiros et al., (2015) found in his study that anxiety, distance and route to college, harassment are substantial factor which affects the academic performance of a student, furthermore, education level of parents and money received by student for expence also have significant impacts on performance of a student.

Academic performance of a student can be affected by personal factors like home or family. Educated and supporting parents will encourage an environment which suits and enhance the study need of a student and will surely enhance the academic performance of a student (Marzano, 2003). Parental involvement pays huge part in the academic performance and enrichment of a student and success in their academic goals and to get higher results (Barnard, 2004).

1.3 Academic factors

Higher expectations, academic pressure, information over-load, impractical aspirations, restrained chances of development, and a higher competitive environment are a few roots of stress which produce anxiety, unrest, dread and worry among students (Sinha, 2001).

Nkum (2015) disclosed that learning syllabus, inadequate teaching methods, lower self-motivation, lecturer's method of teaching are some aspects which affect the academic performance of a student.

Furthermore, Adequateness, availableness and accessibility of learning resource determine the affectivity of learning procedure in an institution. Learning resources and educational activities increase the apprehension of curriculum, ideas and enhance the performance of a pupil (Schneider, 2002). Equivalently, Reche (2012) discovered that books aid and enables the students to clearly emphasize the syllabus presentations of teachers.

Institutions that spend less money and efforts to purchase adequate teaching and other essential resources perform poorly. Libraries and laboratories should be furnished with appropriate and adequate book, materials, apparatus and equipment.

1.4 Environmental factors

Environmental factor was not considered as an influential factor for academic performance earlier. But from the over the last decade many studies have been conducted in this regard and most of them have concluded that environmental factors have significant affects on the academic performance of a student.

Surrounding environment plays a key role in the development of an individual whether he is a student, teacher, parent, professional or related to any other field of life. In the life of a student environmental factors are essential for his or her development and academic performance. Many studies have found the psychological and physiological potentials of a student are affected at a greater level by environmental factors. Some environmental factors such as; inadequate schooling facilities, misuse of technology including internet and institution environment significantly and negatively affect the overall academic performance of a student.

Location of institution is one of the vital environmental factors which affect the academic performance of students at a greater level. Onukwo (2005) stated that peaceful and favorable environment is contributive towards the development and enhancement of a student. Whereas, institutions situated at noisy urban areas are linked with deficits and lack of concentration of a student leading towards the lower academic performance.

Academic success of a student's is based on his environment and as well as his personal skills. Supporting instructors at college, family members, society, community and friends are some of the key environmental factors for quality education and enhanced academic performance. These factors play a vital role in enrichment and improved academic performance and achievement of academic goals of a student (Goddard, 2003)

1.5 Student's performance

In this age of modernization and technical advancement, education is regarded as commencing pace for most of the human and earthly activities. It contributes predominantly to the enhancement of human capital and is associated with a person's wellbeing and opportunities for enriched endure (Battle, 2002). This assures the acquirement of wisdom and competence which enables a person to

enhance their earning and productivity and elevate their living standards. Increased productivity also enables additional earning which ultimately contributes toward the economic betterment of the country (Saxton, 2000). Student's performance can also be called academic performance. Academic performance is a academic goal set by the university or institution and accomplished by the student through the guidance of a mentor in a specific frame of time.

Instructors, teachers and investigators have long been keen to discover and know different aspects affecting student's performance. There are many factors which are contributing positively and negatively towards the performance of the students, some are which are from school inside like; student factors, house factors, academic factors and relation with other students (Crosnoe, 2004).

Academic performance of a student is seen as a indicator of future success and career prosperity of that student. Higher academic performance ensures the better GPA of a student and in most of the cases higher GPA is regarded a sign of higher intellectual capabilities and better understanding of subject matter in that individual.

Furthermore, higher academic performance also boosts the confidence levels of a student, which is essential to tackle any obstacle in the way of successful and prosper professional life.

This study is conducted to measure the impacts and stress on student's performance in higher educational institutions of Khairpur Mir's. As discussed and portrayed above by referencing studies of different researcher on different aspect, factors, conditions, situations and causes of stress it is denoted that stress among higher education students is nothing new to study. Many studies have stated that stress is a significant and negative aspect of students life and it can not be denied that stress does affects and impacts the performance of students of higher education institutions of Khairpur Mirs.

1.6 Problem Statement

Majority of students' intake in universities of Sindh are from the remote areas, even from weak and non-structured academic background. Mostly in first year students feel depressed to face the new environment of the universities, hostel life, learning burden.

Students could not manage their academic responsibilities in proper manner. Their physical and psychological problems during first year of study they under go into academic stress. Some time they leave the university or they divert their programs by wasting their educational years by changing the universities. In this regard in universities academic management becomes a challenge.

1.7 Research Objectives

1. To examine the effect of personal factors on students' performance.
2. To analyze the effect academic factors and students' performance.
3. To identify the effect of environmental factors on students' performance.

1.8 Research Questions

- Q1:** What are affects of personal factors on students' performance?
Q2: How do academic factors cause a change in students' performance?
Q3: What is the major affect of environmental factors on students' performance?

1.9 Scope of the Study

This study is important for all the stake holders related with the students' academic performance and achievement. This study will help the university administration, students, parents and other common people to cope with the stress. It will help the management in planning certain programs to prevent the students from stress. This will also help students to face the academic and environmental challenges in effective manner.

2. Literature Review

Life of a university student can be viewed as felicitous time, yet it can be very stressful and full of anxiety for many pupils. Many studies have been conducted to investigate and explore the academic stress and its impact on the performance of a students, many researchers have explained "stress" as incompetency of coping with the demands and requiriements of surrounding environment (Mani, 2010). In this case surround environment is higher educational institutes of Khairpur Mirs.

Stress is the procedure at which a person reverts during unlocked to external or internal obstacles and challenges. The living things process many systems to relate such adjusting return through both systematic and natural level. Through this stress has just effect on the brain and the entire the structure of the body, when an individual fail to qualify the stressful condition the outcome result can be brain breakdown, physiological dilemma it included depression nervousness soreness tiredness (Shadi M, 2018)

Reproduction, cardiovascular, metabolism and gastrointestinal these are all the form of stress related diseases in the field of the physiologically, and analysis by huge area of the genetic and enlightening factors , and these factors can be different from person to person, but sign of the affliction seems to be same upon the persons (Hellhammer, 2008)

Wheeler (2007) describe that stress is related to the physics it related to the force which is applied to the object in real life as to how obstacles affect on the human and it carry force used on the human life. Some of these are financial difficulties, health issues, clash with friends, these all transport force and pressure on human body and mind. Some of the pressure derives from the environment but most of the them generated by the human mind and this can be form of nervousness, trouble, sorrow, depressed and despondency.

Basically stress is a negative force which applied to a person and outcome result in a pain and this pain is outcome of non governed stress when a person cannot handle the problems as well as pain. When somebody have a ability to face the obstacles and fight the pain result that person is slightest effected while in same situation somebody has no ability to go through the pressure and pain that kind of people cannot survive and effected maximal (Khan, 2013).

According to the Parogram (2006) stress is the doubtful respond facing into outside and within factors, that method and negative or positive respond to surroundings provocation. Through this total human body get changes and strange situation that present in the series of time. In this period of time many hormonal reactions are at maximum level. And the body react rapidly and many health issue occur in the body some of them are heart rate, blood pressure, stroke volume

According to the Hackman Oldham, (1974) stress has two aspects one is eustress and second one is distress first one is positive and second one is negative. Stress is most important topic which talked and discussed in today's time. Stress is rapidly affected to all in different way, individual, group of people and organizations cannot be stay unaffected.

In the literature review, Stress arises as the main factor in the business world. There are many applications which related to stress including attrition overhead costs, moral and poor productivity, that's why many research have analyzed the stress and its dimension (Nur Hamizah Hj Ramli 1, 2018). Minter, (1999) describe that the stress negative physical and emotional results and these results arise when necessities of a career do not sport the qualification and resources.

University life is treated to be a joyful time, but despite of it that time can be very stressful and confrontation for all the students .Newton describe that students go through from stress. Many researchers examined the stress, and they analyzed in various ways. Many researchers describe that stress is a impetus and problematic state.

Stress occur when the demands and capacity on the huge difference. Gunnar (1998) stated the academic stress this type of the stress arises from the schooling and education. The compressions between degree and education in the form of homework, tests, labs, reading and quizzes can be cause of stress. Every students face the stress during the doing all of the work balancing the time and facing the time curricular activities (Aikens, 1992). Students go through the stresses that are away from the home in that sense academic stress is very hard on school students. The cause of stress can be the expectation of teachers regarding work completed on time and students do not fulfill the demand and expectations of the teacher the stress arise in that situation.

Many researches, books workshops and famous articles are trying to the teach to the individuals how to face and handle that, because many stress dimension such as tension depression found as a common problem among the youth. Researchers are doing work on this subject in different ways, some researchers describe that the stress factor has immediate impacts and some Researchers state that stress also side effects. For suppose time pressure

limits for a particular task to achieve, this limit considered as the physical limit not included in psychological this comprehend with immediate effects. When this limitation cause of the emotional reaction, considered the nervousness which has the side effects and have direct impact on success. this two effects of the stress and effort done in the main literature (Egget, 2000).

According to the Baumeister, (2000) enlightened on the complex concept of stress, and describe the how stress impacts the human in terms of academic performance and other performance. The properties of direct and indirect different factors which created

stress. Direct stress dose not included in psychology and it effects experienced by the goal volume, stress that may also be caused. (Fliege, 2005) Indirect stress included in psychology it related with task load requirements. These two effects likely to be same and their measurement is very difficult and some time it become challenging to distinguish between them. Shaikh (2004) stated that the stress is the the state of pain and this pain related to the mental or emotional and also the reaction of the body which are designed for the self peservation. According to the Hoe (2003) stress is the daily requested which is linked to the changes it relate to the mentally as well as physically reaction.

3.1 Research Model

3.2 Research Hypotheses

H1: There is positive significant relationship between personal factors and students' performance.

H2: A significant change in academic factors causes a positive change in students' performance.

H3: There is significant positive relationship between environmental factors and students' performance.

4. Research Methods

4.1 Sampling Design

The data for this study were collected from the first year students of Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur and Benazir Bhutto Shaheed University of Technical and Skills Development Khairpur Mirs'. The universities visited were located in city area of Khairpur Mirs lying at same road. The students of first year was selected because mostly first year students because of new environment, culture easily under go into stress.

A 35-items scale by Zeidner (1992) was used to measure the effects of stress on students' performance of Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur and BBSUTSD Khairpur. The main items of the scale were the relation with other people, personal factors, academic factors and environmental factors. Items were rated on a five point-likert scale as 1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree. To determine the level of stress towards students' performance in effective manner reliability and validity of the instrument was checked for the current study.

The targeted population for the study was the first year students of Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur and Benazir Bhutto Shaheed University of Technology and Skills Development Khairpur. There are 28 departments in SALU Khairpur with 2765 students in first year and four departments in BBSUTSD Khairpur with 400 students total 3165 students kept as targeted population.

Sample for the study was calculated by using Taro Yamane (1967) formula as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3165}{1 + 3165(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3165}{1 + 7.9125}$$

$$n = \frac{3165}{8.9125}$$

$$n = 355.11$$

About 400 questionnaires were distributed among the first year students of both universities, from which 340 questionnaires were returned completely filled and were used for further analysis.

5. Analysis

The descriptive statistics were extracted through SPSS 23 Version and the other measurements were conducted by using Smart PLS 3 software. The demographic items were divided into five parts describing the age, gender, university, parents' income and the accommodation they are using. The results of descriptive statistics demonstrate that there were:

While viewing the age profile of the students, 252 students were in the age between 18 to 22 years, 84 were in the age of 23-26 years and 4 students were of the age of 26 and above. Gender wise profile 211 boys and 129 girls students have participated in questionnaire filling. 199 students from SALU Khairpur and 141 students from BBSUTSD Khairpur have participated. 177 students were hostlers, 144 students having their own home and rest of were accommodated in rented homes or hostels.

Further collected data was analyzed through partial least square used to measure the research model hypotheses. PLS model was structured to solve a variant of multiple regressions. Moreover, bootstrapping method in smart PLS was used to measure the significance level, loadings. Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability was also analyzed for measuring the degree of internal consistency.

Table 1: Factor Loadings, Sample Mean, Standard Deviation, P Values

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
AF4 < Academic Factors	0.721	0.722	0.032	22.375	0.000
AF5 < Academic Factors	0.725	0.722	0.040	18.158	0.000
AF6 < Academic Factors	0.729	0.728	0.036	20.511	0.000
AF7 < Academic Factors	0.825	0.823	0.023	35.812	0.000

EF1 <- Environmental Factors	0.746	0.745	0.037	20.024	0.000
EF2 <- Environmental Factors	0.863	0.863	0.016	53.719	0.000
EF3 <- Environmental Factors	0.739	0.737	0.040	18.539	0.000
EF6 <- Environmental Factors	0.694	0.694	0.034	20.192	0.000
PF1 <- Personal Factors	0.673	0.668	0.065	10.416	0.000
PF2 <- Personal Factors	0.635	0.627	0.089	7.139	0.000
PF3 <- Personal Factors	0.814	0.809	0.026	31.379	0.000
PF4 <- Personal Factors	0.798	0.795	0.035	22.933	0.000
PF5 <- Personal Factors	0.755	0.750	0.057	13.167	0.000
SP1 <- Students' Performance	0.704	0.702	0.039	18.082	0.000
SP2 <- Students' Performance	0.822	0.820	0.024	34.920	0.000
SP3 <- Students' Performance	0.707	0.708	0.038	18.534	0.000
SP4 <- Students' Performance	0.778	0.776	0.029	26.789	0.000
SP5 <- Students' Performance	0.644	0.644	0.049	13.235	0.000

The table 1 demonstrates that the factor loadings values for the each constructs are greater than 0.7 with a few constructs having less than 0.7 but almost near to 0.7 as of 0.67 or 0.69. The constructs having

values less than 0.60 were eliminated during analysis. All the variables were met the significance level at 0.000 followed by the sample mean and standard deviation.

Table 2: Construct Reliability, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Academic Factors	0.744	0.761	0.838	0.565
Environmental Factors	0.760	0.772	0.847	0.582
Personal Factors	0.792	0.807	0.856	0.545
Students' Performance	0.783	0.790	0.853	0.538

The results of table 2 demonstrates that the construct and composite reliability meets the cut off value greater than 0.70 (Nunnlay..1978). as shown in results academic factors (AF) with 0.744, Environmental factors (EF) with 0.760, Personal factors (PF) with 0.792 and students’ performance with 0.783 Cronbach’s value respectively. The results also reveal that the AVE values are greater than cutoff value Of 0.50 for each of the constructs (Hair et al., 2013).

5.2 PLS Path Analysis

The figure shows that all three factors of stress have positive and significant impact on the students’ performance ($\beta=0.125^{**}$, $\beta=0.190^{**}$, and $\beta=0.377^{**}$ respectively) Thus all the hypotheses **H1**, **H2**, **H3** were found supported with the significance level of (p values at=0.004, 0.000 and 0.029 respectively. On the other hand the results of table 4, reveal that the endogenous variable (students’ performance) was 0.344 (34.4%) predicated by the independent variables (personal factors, academic factors, environmental factors).

6. Conclusion and Discussion

The major purpose of this study was to measure the impact of stress on students' performance in higher educational institutes of Khairpur Mirs'. The statistical findings of this study presented in-depth concern about how first year students affected by stress. The study has also conducted to find out the significant relationship among stress factors and students' performance. The study was quantitative in nature supported by structured questionnaire driven from prior literature. Results were measured through Smart PLS.

According to analysis, stress factors: personal factors, academic factors and environmental factors have positive and statistical significant on students' performance.

It is cleared from the analysis that if the family don't involve the first year students in their family issues the students' performance will move in proper instance. On the other hand peace full environment free from any kind of violation inside university premises and positive support from administration may also bring positive change in attitude and students' performance. If the institutions equipped with modern teaching aids will also nourish the first year students' performance.

The study findings also backing prior research analysis which was conducted in different cultures, different prospects. Various studies findings also revealed the positive and significant impact of stress factors on students' performance (shahmohammadi, 2011; Ssenyonga, 2014; Calaguas, 2012).

6.1 Limitations and Future Directions

The study has tried to cover the all aspects of research type but as the research is an endless activity so the study has posed certain limitations and drawn a direction for the future researchers in the following aspects.

➤ The study conducted in Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur a general university and MBBSUTSD dealing in technical programs it would be better to conduct comparative study of universities or future researcher may precede it and may also include the medical and engineering students' performance in same context.

➤ The study was Quantitative in nature purely. So future research may be conducted by using mixed methodology or by using different methods of data collection i-e: observation, in-depth interviews, activity based.

The study was conducted only on three stress factors; future research may be conducted by adding other stress factors as relation with other people, psychological factors, physical factors etc.

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